

CAUSATION

International Journal of Science

Black holes and electromagnetism

Research article

Ilija Barukčić¹

¹ Internist, Horandstrasse, 26441 Jever, Germany

* **Correspondence:** E-Mail: Barukcic@t-online.de;
Tel: +49-4466-333; Fax: +49-4466-333.

Impressum:

CAUSATION

International Journal Of Science

Chief-Editor / V. i. S. d. P.:

Ilija Barukčić

Hegelitzer Str. 22

DE-26409 Wittmund-Ardorf (Germany)

© Editorial Team: **EDITORIAL TEAM**

🌐 Website: WWW.CAUSATION.EU

✉ E-Mail: editor@causation.eu

☎ Phone: +(49) 4466 - 333

Year: 2025; Volume: 20; Issue: 7; pp. 5–51.

✉ Received: August 1, 2024

✓ Accepted: August 1, 2024

📅 Published: August 18, 2024

📖 [Deutsche Nationalbibliothek Frankfurt](#)

📄 [ISSN: 1863-9542](#)

[DOI:10.5281/zenodo.13337318](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13337318)

🔍 Find in: [Zenodo](#) [Orcid Academia ...](#)

Abstract**BACKGROUND:**

Black holes, enigmatic objects with immense gravitational fields, have long fascinated physicists due to their profound implications for our understanding of gravity and spacetime. Traditionally, black hole physics has been described through solutions of Einstein's field equations, with key contributions from matter and radiation. However, recent studies suggest that the cosmological constant Λ , which characterizes the energy density of the vacuum, plays a crucial role in shaping the geometry of spacetime around black holes.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This study examines the influence of the cosmological constant Λ on the gravitational field of black holes using the Einstein's field equations. Schwarzschild and Kerr-Newman solutions to Einstein's equations, incorporating Λ as a parameter to explore its effects on spacetime curvature and black hole dynamics, were considered. The stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field has been reexamined.

RESULTS:

Our analysis reveals that the cosmological constant Λ significantly impacts the spacetime structure around black holes. A negative Λ generates an attractive force, leading to decelerated expansion or contraction of spacetime, with negative curvature. Notably, in the absence of significant contributions from electromagnetic fields, $\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}$ becomes one dominant factor governing local spacetime dynamics. The stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field has been successfully geometrized. Based on this achievement, the four fundamental fields of nature, $a_{\mu\nu}$, $b_{\mu\nu}$, $c_{\mu\nu}$, $d_{\mu\nu}$, were fully expressed in geometric form.

CONCLUSION:

The investigation highlights the pivotal role of the cosmological constant Λ in determining the local spacetime geometry of black holes. This perspective necessitates a reevaluation of black hole models, integrating Λ as a central component in understanding the structure and evolution of black holes.

Keywords:

Black holes; Gravitation; Cosmological constant; Einstein; Relativity; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k; Causality; Causation

☺ Reviewer 1: None/Author.

☺ Reviewer 2: None.

☺ Reviewer 3: None.

1. Introduction

The theoretical notion of black holes, objects with gravitational fields so strong that even electromagnetic waves, such as light, cannot escape, has intrigued scientists at least since the 18th century. The earliest documented theoretical discussions of such extraordinary entities can be attributed to John Michell (see [Michell, 1784](#), p. 50) and Pierre-Simon Laplace (see [Laplace, 1796, 1799](#)), Napoleon's examiner when Napoleon graduated at the *École Militaire* in Paris in 1785 (see [Hankins, 2006](#)). Michell himself, in 1783, hypothesized about the existence of dark stars whose escape velocity would exceed the speed of light, thus rendering them invisible. This idea was further developed by Laplace, who speculated about similar objects in his work on celestial mechanics. The modern understanding of black holes began to take shape with Karl Schwarzschild's solution (see [Schwarzschild, 1916](#)) to Einstein's field equations in 1916, which described the structure of such an object under general relativity. Schwarzschild's solution revealed the possibility of a region in spacetime from which nothing could escape, thus laying the theoretical groundwork for what we now call a black hole. In 1958, David Finkelstein advanced the interpretation of black holes as regions where the escape of light and other forms of radiation is impossible, effectively coining the term black hole (see [Finkelstein, 1958](#)). Despite these theoretical advancements, black holes were initially regarded as mathematical curiosities rather than real astrophysical entities. It wasn't until the 1960s that the concept gained broader acceptance as a fundamental prediction of general relativity, supported by robust theoretical frameworks. The discovery of neutron stars by Jocelyn Bell Burnell in 1967 further fueled interest in gravitationally collapsed objects, suggesting that such extreme entities could indeed exist (see [Burnell, 1967](#)). Finally, the first observational confirmation (see [Webster and Murdin, 1972](#); [Bolton, 1972](#)) of a black hole came in 1971 with the identification of Cygnus X-1, marking a significant milestone in our understanding of these enigmatic physical objects.

According to Einstein's theory of general relativity, a mass that is sufficiently compact can warp a region of spacetime to such a degree that it creates a region where gravity is so intense that not even light (electromagnetic wave) itself can escape. Within this region, the curvature of spacetime is so extreme that it prevents any form of matter or radiation from escaping, a phenomenon known as a black hole.

As a physical entity approaches the event horizon of a black hole, electromagnetic radiation, like all other forms of radiation and matter, becomes increasingly redshifted and stretched. At the event horizon due to the extreme warping of spacetime, electromagnetic waves just like light cannot escape. However, inside the event horizon the existence of electromagnetic fields and radiation that crossed the event horizon, need not come to an end. While electromagnetism is not excluded from black holes, the behavior electromagnetism inside the event horizon might be profoundly altered by the extreme gravitational effects. Quantum field theory in curved spacetime introduces the concept of Hawking radiation (see [Hawking, 1974](#)), predicting that event horizons might emit some radiation that can be detected outside the event horizon itself.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

The following discussion adhere, as far as possible, to Einstein's view of the relationship between matter and the gravitational field. Einstein himself defined the gravitational field **ex negativo** as follows.

“Wir unterscheiden im folgenden zwischen ‘Gravitationsfeld’ und ‘Materie’, in dem Sinne, daß **alles außer dem Gravitationsfeld als ‘Materie’ bezeichnet** wird, also nicht nur die ‘Materie’ im üblichen Sinne, sondern auch das elektromagnetische Feld. ”

(Einstein, 1916, p. 802/803)

Here is the translation of the given Einstein's text into English: ‘We distinguish in the following between gravitational field and matter, in the sense that everything except the gravitational field is regarded as ‘matter’, that is not only ‘matter in the ordinary sense’, but also the ‘electromagnetic field.’ In other words, Einstein demands that matter is ‘... matter in the ordinary sense, but also the electromagnetic field.’. The following and only symbolic figure might illustrate the relationship between matter, ordinary matter and the electromagnetic field in more detail.

Electromagnetic field $b_{\mu\nu}$.

Ordinary Matter $a_{\mu\nu}$

$$\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}$$

In brief, to make it clear and explicit:

“... a tensor, $T_{\mu\nu}$, of the second rank ... includes in itself the energy density of the electromagnetic field and of ponderable matter; we shall denote this in the following as the ‘energy tensor of matter’”

(Einstein, 1923, pp. 87/88)

Therefore, the Einstein's field equations are give as

$$G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} \quad (1)$$

where $R_{\mu\nu}$ is the Ricci tensor (Ricci-Curbastro and Levi-Civita, 1900) of ‘Einstein’s general theory of relativity’ (Einstein, 1916), R is the Ricci scalar, the trace of the Ricci curvature tensor with respect to the metric and equally the simplest curvature invariant of a Riemannian manifold, Λ is the Einstein’s cosmological (Einstein, 1917; Barukčić, 2015a) constant, $\underline{\Lambda}$ is the “**anti cosmological constant**” (Barukčić, 2015a), $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor of Einstein’s general theory of relativity, $G_{\mu\nu}$ is Einstein’s curvature tensor, $\underline{G}_{\mu\nu}$ is the “**anti tensor**” (Barukčić, 2016c) of Einstein’s curvature tensor, $E_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor of energy, $\underline{E}_{\mu\nu}$ is the tensor of non-energy, the anti-tensor of the stress-energy tensor of energy, $a_{\mu\nu}$, $b_{\mu\nu}$, $c_{\mu\nu}$ and $d_{\mu\nu}$ denote the four basic fields of nature were $a_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor of ordinary matter, $b_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field, c is the speed of the light in vacuum, γ is Newton’s gravitational “**constant**” (Barukčić, 2015b,a, 2016a,c), π is Archimedes constant pi. In the following, we will see that the relationship of the four basic fields of nature, denoted as $a_{\mu\nu}$, $b_{\mu\nu}$, $c_{\mu\nu}$, $d_{\mu\nu}$, is given as illustrated by the following picture:

Table 1 provide a more detailed and preliminary overview (Barukčić, 2016c,b) of what is to follow.

		Curvature		
		YES	NO	
Momentum	YES	$a_{\mu\nu}$	$b_{\mu\nu} \equiv (c_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$	$\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \times g_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} - \frac{R}{2} + \Lambda\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$
	NO	$c_{\mu\nu} \equiv (b_{\mu\nu} - \Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$	$d_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu} - b_{\mu\nu}\right)$	$\left(\frac{R}{2} - \Lambda\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$
		$G_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} - \frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$	$\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}$	$R_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{R}{D} \times g_{\mu\nu}$

Table 1. Four basic fields of nature and the Einstein’s field equations.

Einstein’s field equations might be defined in space-time dimensions (see Málek, 2012, p. 31) other than 3+1 too.

2.2. Methods

Definitions

The four basic fields of nature

The four basic fields of nature are defined as $a_{\mu\nu}$, $b_{\mu\nu}$, $c_{\mu\nu}$, $d_{\mu\nu}$ where:

1. $a_{\mu\nu}$: is the stress-energy tensor of ordinary matter,
2. $b_{\mu\nu}$: is the stress-energy tensor of electromagnetic field,
3. $c_{\mu\nu}$: is the Einstein's tensor ($G_{\mu\nu}$) without the stress-energy tensor of ordinary matter $a_{\mu\nu}$,
4. $d_{\mu\nu}$: is the tensor ($\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}$) without the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field $b_{\mu\nu}$,

The Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$

The Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ is determined by the four basic fields of nature as

$$R_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} \quad (2)$$

The unification of fundamental forces has been a significant goal in theoretical physics. Meanwhile, the electromagnetic force and the weak force have been successfully unified into a single framework known as the electroweak theory. This unification was achieved through the work of Sheldon Glashow, Abdus Salam, and Steven Weinberg (see [Glashow, 1970](#); [Weinberg, 1977](#); [Salam, 1979](#); [Georgi and Glashow, 1974](#)), for which they were awarded the Nobel Prize in Physics in 1979.

The strong nuclear force, or strong interaction, is the fundamental force responsible for binding protons and neutrons together within atomic nuclei. It is mediated by particles called gluons, which interact with quarks, the building blocks of protons and neutrons. This force is characterized by its short range but extremely high strength, significantly stronger than the electromagnetic force. The strong force operates at distances on the order of femtometers (10^{-15} meters) and ensures the stability of atomic nuclei. The weak nuclear force, or weak interaction, is responsible for the process of beta decay in atomic nuclei, among other phenomena. It is mediated by the W and Z bosons. The weak force has a much shorter range than the strong force and is weaker in comparison. It plays a crucial role in the nuclear fusion processes that power stars and is vital for the stability of matter at the atomic level.

Unification of the Strong and Weak Forces: The unification of the strong and weak forces into something like an ordinary force could turn out to become a significant goal in theoretical physics. Unifying the strong and weak forces is one among the crucial steps towards integrating gravity into a single framework, leading to theories like string theory or loop quantum gravity and other.

The Einstein's field equations

The left-hand side of the Einstein field equations encapsulates the geometric properties of spacetime, while the right-hand side relates these to the matter and energy content of the universe. These equations are given as:

$$G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \quad (3)$$

(see [Einstein, 1916](#), pp. 769–822)

where:

- $G_{\mu\nu}$ is the Einstein tensor, representing the curvature of spacetime.
- Λ is the cosmological constant, which accounts for the energy density of empty space, or "dark energy."
- $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor, describing the geometry of spacetime.
- $T_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor of matter, representing the distribution and flow of energy and momentum in spacetime.
- G is the gravitational constant, a fundamental physical constant describing the strength of gravity.
- c is the speed of light in a vacuum, a universal physical constant.

Stress-Energy Tensor of the Electromagnetic Field

The stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field (see [Misner et al., 1973](#), p. 140) describes the distribution of energy, momentum, and stress within an electromagnetic field. It plays a crucial role in the theory of electromagnetism, particularly in the context of general relativity, where it acts as a source term in Einstein's field equations. In general, the stress-energy tensor ${}_{\text{EM}} T_{\mu\nu}$ for the electromagnetic field is given by:

$${}_{\text{EM}} T_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}{}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \right) = b_{\mu\nu} \quad (4)$$

where $F_{\mu\nu}$ is the electromagnetic field tensor (see [Maxwell, 1865](#)), $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor, and μ_0 is the permeability of free space. The tensor accounts for the energy density of the electromagnetic field (see [Larmor, 1900](#)), as well as the flux of energy and momentum.

Axioms

In general, axioms might serve as the fundamental building blocks from which laws or theorems can be derived. However, it is necessary that axioms are self-evident truths which can be accepted without proof and which can be used to derive further truths within a given system. In the following, we propose three essential axioms often denoted as: Axiom I (Lex Identitatis), Axiom II (Lex Contradictionis), and Axiom III (Lex Negationis). These axioms—Lex Identitatis, Lex Contradictionis, and Lex Negationis—form the bedrock of any scientific reasoning. Axiom I ensures that entities are consistent with themselves, Axiom II prevents contradictions within a scientific systems, and Axiom III provides a mechanism to reconcile contrary positions. Together, they create a robust framework for deductive reasoning and logical analysis, enabling the development of complex theories and systems based on these fundamental principles.

DEFINITION 1. Lex Identitatis.

Axiom I, also known as Lex Identitatis, states that an entity is equal to itself. Formally, Lex Identitatis can be expressed as:

AXIOM No. 1 (Lex Identitatis). $1 = 1$

Explanation: This axiom asserts the principle of identity, which is foundational to logical reasoning and mathematics. It implies that each element is identical to itself, a basic property that underpins the consistency of mathematical operations and logical deductions. This self-evidence is crucial because it allows us to state and work with equations and identities with the assurance that elements are consistent and unchanging.

DEFINITION 2. Lex Contradictionis.

Axiom II, or Lex Contradictionis, is formulated as:

AXIOM No. 2 (Lex Contradictionis). $0 = 1$

Explanation: This axiom states that something cannot simultaneously be and not be in the same respect.

DEFINITION 3. Lex Negationis

Axiom III, also known as Lex Negationis, is expressed as:

AXIOM No. 3 (Lex Negationis). $-0 = 1$

Explanation: In general, the negation of the negation of an entity A implies formally A itself.

3. Results

Scalars and Einstein's field equations $G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}$

For any general matter distribution, the stress-energy tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$ can be represented as a 4×4 matrix:

$$T_{\mu\nu} = \begin{bmatrix} T_{00} & T_{01} & T_{02} & T_{03} \\ T_{10} & T_{11} & T_{12} & T_{13} \\ T_{20} & T_{21} & T_{22} & T_{23} \\ T_{30} & T_{31} & T_{32} & T_{33} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where the components $T_{\mu\nu}$ depend on the particular matter and energy content of the system. Similarly, the contravariant stress-energy tensor $T^{\mu\nu}$ is given by:

$$T^{\mu\nu} = \begin{bmatrix} T^{00} & T^{01} & T^{02} & T^{03} \\ T^{10} & T^{11} & T^{12} & T^{13} \\ T^{20} & T^{21} & T^{22} & T^{23} \\ T^{30} & T^{31} & T^{32} & T^{33} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where the components $T^{\mu\nu}$ are obtained by raising the indices of $T_{\mu\nu}$ using the metric tensor $g^{\mu\nu}$ as follows:

$$T^{\mu\nu} = g^{\mu\alpha} g^{\nu\beta} T_{\alpha\beta} \quad (7)$$

where $g^{\mu\nu}$ is the inverse metric tensor. As next, we multiply the stress-energy tensor of matter by scalars in order to obtain

$$\frac{e}{e} \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) T_{\mu\nu} = e \times \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{e \times c^4}\right) \begin{bmatrix} T_{00} & T_{01} & T_{02} & T_{03} \\ T_{10} & T_{11} & T_{12} & T_{13} \\ T_{20} & T_{21} & T_{22} & T_{23} \\ T_{30} & T_{31} & T_{32} & T_{33} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

The question is, can this be equivalent to something like:

$$\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) T_{\mu\nu} = e \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (9)$$

where $g_{\mu\nu}$ would be the metric tensor of the stress-energy tensor of matter. Under these circumstances, the field itself could be geometrized. As a consequence, must we potentially give up the symmetry condition of the metric tensor, $g_{\mu\nu} = g_{\nu\mu}$ of general relativity. In general relativity, the symmetry condition of the metric tensor, $g_{\mu\nu} = g_{\nu\mu}$, is crucial because the same ensures that the geometric structure of spacetime are consistent and well-defined. Furthermore, the symmetry condition of the metric tensor, $g_{\mu\nu} = g_{\nu\mu}$ of general relativity guarantees that distances and angles are measured correctly and that the curvature of spacetime, as described by the metric tensor, behaves consistently. Without such a symmetry, it is possible that the fundamental concepts such as the interval between events and the Einstein field equations could become mathematically inconsistent, leading to an unreliable description of gravitational phenomena. Ultimately, the pressing question is whether more special tensors like ${}_e g_{\mu\nu}$ are needed and are more appropriate for describing such entities. One should not preempt the further discussion and scientific reception of this matter at this point. Regardless of the outcome of this discussion, it does not change the fact that the descriptions of general relativity can be fully and logically consistent, without epistemological discrepancies or losses, when described using scalar quantities. In this natural law, we aim to investigate whether it is at least theoretically possible to express the entirety of Einstein's field equations using scalars, without leading to contradictions or loss of information. As an example, we investigate the stress-energy tensor.

NUMERUS LEGIS NATURALIS: 1 (EINSTEIN'S FIELD EQUATIONS AND SCALARS). The tensors of Einstein's theory of relativity can be fully expressed in geometrical terms.

Proof by Direct Proof. To begin this proof, we acknowledge the general validity of the fundamental identity:

$$1 = 1 \quad (10)$$

Next, we multiply equation 10 by the stress-energy tensor of matter $\left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}\right)$ itself, and recognize that the stress-energy tensor of matter is identical to itself too and given by:

$$\left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}\right) = \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}\right) \quad (11)$$

According to our understanding, it should be possible to express the stress-energy tensor of matter using only scalars and the metric tensor of general relativity, without leading to contradictions or inconsistencies with Einstein's theory. In other words, it is generally valid that

$$\left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}\right) = \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times \text{scalar}_x \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (12)$$

Next, we take the trace of equation 12 and obtain:

$$\left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}\right) g^{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times \text{scalar}_x \times g_{\mu\nu} g^{\mu\nu} \quad (13)$$

It is known that $g_{\mu\nu} g^{\mu\nu} = D$. Equation 13 simplifies to:

$$\left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T\right) = \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times \text{scalar}_x \times D \quad (14)$$

where T is known as Laue's scalar. We rearrange equation 14 to find the sought scalar that ensures compatibility with Einstein's general relativity as

$$\text{scalar}_x = \left(\frac{T}{D}\right) \quad (15)$$

In other words, it is generally true that

$$\left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}\right) = \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times \text{scalar}_x \times g_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times \left(\frac{T}{D}\right)\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (16)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

This proof demonstrates the theoretical possibility of expressing the stress-energy tensor of matter using scalars and the metric tensor in a manner consistent with Einstein's general theory of relativity. At the same time, the proof serves as an example and is specifically valid and applicable to the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field as well as to other tensors in general relativity. For instance, consider: $\underline{E}_{\mu\nu} = \underline{e} \times g_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{R}{2} - \Lambda\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$. It necessarily follows that: $\underline{e} = \left(\frac{R}{2} - \Lambda\right)$. By showing that these expressions do not lead to contradictions or inconsistencies, the proof highlights the flexibility in accommodating different mathematical formulations of objective reality while preserving its foundational principles. This proof underscores the robustness of these alternative methods and their compatibility with Einstein's theory while representing physical quantities of objective reality. In the framework of general relativity, the gravitational effects of matter and energy are interpreted as manifestations of the curvature of spacetime rather than forces acting at a distance. This approach radically changed the understanding of gravity from a force in Newtonian mechanics to a geometric property of spacetime itself. As known, the stress-energy tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$ describes the distribution of matter and energy in spacetime, and the Einstein field equations relate this tensor to the curvature of spacetime through the Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$. However, geometrizing matter itself means that matter might be determined by the geometry of spacetime itself. This perspective leads to a new and profound understanding the fabric of spacetime. Such an approach has other and significant consequences: it unifies the descriptions of gravitational phenomena with the geometry of spacetime, providing a more comprehensive framework for understanding objective reality. Additionally, it will necessitate revisions in our understanding of nature, influencing theories even about the origin and evolution of the universe. Moreover, the strategic potential of geometrizing matter itself extends to the pursuit of a unified field theory. If all fundamental forces of nature—gravity, electromagnetism, the weak nuclear force, the strong nuclear force et cetera—can be described in terms of geometric structures, it should become possible to formulate a logically consistent unified field theory. Such a unified field theory would aim to integrate these diverse forces into a single theoretical framework, potentially leading to a more profound understanding of the fundamental interactions governing objective reality. By geometrizing all natural fields, we might uncover a deeper symmetry underlying the fabric of reality, paving the way for a more cohesive theory that encompasses all physical phenomena. This unification could not only consolidate our understanding of objective reality but also guide future research and experimental efforts in science and physics.

Derivation of the electromagnetic stress-energy tensor

As next, we will try to derive the electromagnetic stress-energy tensor by varying the Maxwell action with respect to the metric.

NUMERUS LEGIS NATURALIS: 2 (THE STRESS-ENERGY TENSOR OF THE ELECTROMAGNETIC FIELD). The stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field is given as:

$${}_{\text{EM}}T_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \right) = b_{\mu\nu} \quad (17)$$

where:

- $F_{\mu\nu}$ is the covariant electromagnetic tensor or electromagnetic field tensor (sometimes called the field strength tensor, Faraday tensor or Maxwell bivector) which describes the electromagnetic field in spacetime. The Faraday tensor $F_{\mu\nu}$ (also called the electromagnetic field strength tensor) is defined as:

$$F_{\mu\nu} = \partial_{\mu} A_{\nu} - \partial_{\nu} A_{\mu}$$

where A_{μ} is the electromagnetic potential. The tensor is antisymmetric:

$$F_{\mu\nu} = -F_{\nu\mu}$$

This antisymmetry implies that the trace of $F_{\mu\nu}$ is zero in any number of dimensions:

$$F^{\mu}_{\mu} = 0$$

- $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor, describing the geometry of spacetime.
- $g^{\mu\nu}$ is the inverse metric tensor, describing the geometry of spacetime.
- ${}_{\text{EM}}T_{\mu\nu}$ i. e. $b_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field, representing the distribution and flow of energy and momentum in spacetime due to the electromagnetic field.

Proof by Direct Proof. We begin this proof by acknowledging the validity of the fundamental identity:

$$1 = 1 \quad (18)$$

We continue by multiplying equation 18 by the action for the electromagnetic field given as: $S_{\text{EM}}[g_{\mu\nu}, A_{\mu}] = -\frac{1}{4\mu_0} \int d^4x \sqrt{-g} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}$

where:

- $F_{\alpha\beta} = \partial_\alpha A_\beta - \partial_\beta A_\alpha$ is the electromagnetic field tensor.
- $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor, describing the geometry of spacetime.
- $g^{\mu\nu}$ is the inverse metric tensor, describing the geometry of spacetime.
- ${}_{\text{EM}}T_{\mu\nu}$ i. e. $b_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field, representing the distribution and flow of energy and momentum in spacetime due to the electromagnetic field.

The action for the electromagnetic field is:

$$S_{\text{EM}}[g_{\mu\nu}, A_\mu] = -\frac{1}{4\mu_0} \int d^4x \sqrt{-g} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \quad (19)$$

To find the stress-energy tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$, we vary the action with respect to the metric $g^{\mu\nu}$:

$$T_{\mu\nu} = -2 \frac{\delta S_{\text{EM}}}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}} \quad (20)$$

The variation of the action is:

$$\frac{\delta}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}} (\sqrt{-g} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}) = \frac{\delta(\sqrt{-g})}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} + \sqrt{-g} \frac{\delta(F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta})}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}} \quad (21)$$

The variation of $\sqrt{-g}$ is:

$$\frac{\delta(\sqrt{-g})}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}} = -\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{-g} g_{\mu\nu} \quad (22)$$

The variation of $F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}$ is:

$$\frac{\delta(F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta})}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}} = 2F_{\mu\sigma} F_\nu{}^\sigma \quad (23)$$

Combining these variations, we get:

$$\frac{\delta(\sqrt{-g} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta})}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}} = -\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{-g} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} + \sqrt{-g} \cdot 2F_{\mu\sigma} F_\nu{}^\sigma \quad (24)$$

Substitute into the formula for $T_{\mu\nu}$:

$$T_{\mu\nu} = -2 \left[-\frac{1}{4\mu_0} \left(-\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{-g} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} + \sqrt{-g} \cdot 2F_{\mu\sigma} F_\nu{}^\sigma \right) \right] \quad (25)$$

Simplify to obtain:

$$T_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(F_{\mu\alpha} F_\nu{}^\alpha - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \right) \quad (26)$$

where we included the factor $\frac{1}{\mu_0}$ to match the units in the International System of Units (SI).

Quod erat demonstrandum.

Derivation of the trace of the electromagnetic stress-energy tensor

NUMERUS LEGIS NATURALIS: 3 (The Trace of the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field). The Trace of the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field is given as

$${}_{\text{EM}}T = g^{\mu\nu}T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{2}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{4-D}{4} \right) \left(\left(\frac{\mathbf{E}^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{B}^2 \right) \right) \right) \quad (27)$$

Proof by Direct Proof. We begin this proof by acknowledging the validity of the fundamental identity:

$$1 = 1 \quad (28)$$

We continue by multiplying equation 28 by $T_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} (F_{\mu\alpha}F_{\nu}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4}g_{\mu\nu}F_{\alpha\beta}F^{\alpha\beta})$. In other words, the electromagnetic stress-energy tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$ of the electromagnetic field in D dimensions is given by:

$$T_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(F_{\mu\alpha}F_{\nu}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4}g_{\mu\nu}F_{\alpha\beta}F^{\alpha\beta} \right) \quad (29)$$

To find the trace of $T_{\mu\nu}$, we compute:

$${}_{\text{EM}}T = g^{\mu\nu}T_{\mu\nu} \quad (30)$$

Substituting the expression for $T_{\mu\nu}$:

$${}_{\text{EM}}T = g^{\mu\nu}T_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(F_{\mu\alpha}F_{\nu}^{\alpha} g^{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{4}g^{\mu\nu}g_{\mu\nu}F_{\alpha\beta}F^{\alpha\beta} \right) \quad (31)$$

In general it is:

$$D = g^{\mu\nu}g_{\mu\nu} \quad (32)$$

Simplifying, we get:

$${}_{\text{EM}}T = g^{\mu\nu}T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} (F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu}) - \left(\frac{1}{4}DF_{\alpha\beta}F^{\alpha\beta} \right) \right) \quad (33)$$

Simplifying again, we get:

$${}_{\text{EM}}T = g^{\mu\nu}T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{4}{4}F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu} \right) - \left(\frac{DF_{\alpha\beta}F^{\alpha\beta}}{4} \right) \right) \quad (34)$$

and equally

$${}_{\text{EM}}T = g^{\mu\nu}T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{4}{4} F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu} \right) - \left(\frac{DF_{\alpha\beta}F^{\alpha\beta}}{4} \right) \right) \quad (35)$$

Rearranging equation 35, we get:

$${}_{\text{EM}}T = g^{\mu\nu}T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{4F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu}}{4} \right) - \left(\frac{DF_{\alpha\beta}F^{\alpha\beta}}{4} \right) \right) \quad (36)$$

Equality of tensor expression

The electromagnetic field tensor $F_{\mu\nu}$ can be contracted with itself. The process of contracting the electromagnetic field tensor with its covariant and contravariant forms results in an invariant quantity, regardless of the metric signature or coordinate system used. This Lorentz-invariant scalar quantity represents the squared magnitude of the field tensor. In other words, by utilizing the metric tensor in this way, the expression $F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu}$ remains invariant under coordinate transformations, ensuring that its physical interpretation is consistent across different reference frames.

LEMMA 1. The quantity $F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu}$ is equal to $F_{\alpha\beta}F^{\alpha\beta}$, demonstrating that it is Lorentz invariant.

Proof by Direct Proof. We start with the expression $F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu}$. By raising and lowering indices with the metric tensor $g^{\mu\alpha}$ and $g_{\nu\beta}$, we can rewrite this as:

$$F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu} = g^{\mu\alpha}g^{\nu\beta}F_{\mu\nu}F_{\alpha\beta} \quad (37)$$

Since $g^{\mu\alpha}$ and $g^{\nu\beta}$ are the components of the metric tensor and do not alter the invariant nature of $F_{\mu\nu}$, this simplifies to:

$$F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu} = F_{\alpha\beta}F^{\alpha\beta} \quad (38)$$

Thus, $F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu}$ is indeed equal to $F_{\alpha\beta}F^{\alpha\beta}$, confirming its Lorentz invariance.

Quod erat demonstrandum.

Therefore, equation 36 becomes

$${}_{\text{EM}}T = g^{\mu\nu}T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{4F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu}}{4} \right) - \left(\frac{DF_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu}}{4} \right) \right) \quad (39)$$

Simplifying equation 39, we get:

$${}_{\text{EM}}T = g^{\mu\nu}T_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{4-D}{4} \right) F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu} \quad (40)$$

Electromagnetic Invariants

Electromagnetic invariants are quantities constructed from the electromagnetic field tensor $F_{\mu\nu}$ that remain unchanged under Lorentz transformations. These invariants provide valuable physical information about the electromagnetic field that is independent of the observer's frame of reference. For instance, the scalar $F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu}$ represents the squared magnitude of the field tensor, capturing the total electromagnetic field strength in a Lorentz-invariant manner. The process of changing indices, such as switching between covariant $F_{\mu\nu}$ and contravariant $F^{\mu\nu}$ forms, follows from the metric tensor, ensuring consistency in tensor equations across different frames. However, the choice of metric signature directly affects the sign of the invariant quantities formed from the electromagnetic field tensor $F_{\mu\nu}$. In the $(-,+,+,+)$ signature convention, the invariant $F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu}$ corresponds to $-2\left(\frac{\mathbf{E}^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{B}^2\right)$, where $\mathbf{E}$ and $\mathbf{B}$ are the electric and magnetic fields, respectively.

LEMMA 2. The value of the invariant $F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu}$ depends on the metric signature convention used, i. e. $(-,+,+,+)$. In our case, it is $F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu} = 2\left(\frac{\mathbf{E}^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{B}^2\right)$.

Proof by Direct Proof. The covariant electromagnetic field tensor $F_{\mu\nu}$ is defined in terms of the electric and magnetic fields as follows:

$$F_{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -\frac{E_x}{c} & -\frac{E_y}{c} & -\frac{E_z}{c} \\ \frac{E_x}{c} & 0 & -B_z & B_y \\ \frac{E_y}{c} & B_z & 0 & -B_x \\ \frac{E_z}{c} & -B_y & B_x & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

where E_x, E_y, E_z are the components of the electric field $\mathbf{E}$, and B_x, B_y, B_z are the components of the magnetic field $\mathbf{B}$. The speed of light c ensures that the electric field components are correctly scaled. To find $F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu}$, we compute $F^{\mu\nu}$, the contravariant form of the field tensor. Given the metric tensor $g^{\mu\nu}$ in Cartesian coordinates:

$$F^{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \frac{E_x}{c} & \frac{E_y}{c} & \frac{E_z}{c} \\ -\frac{E_x}{c} & 0 & -B_z & B_y \\ -\frac{E_y}{c} & B_z & 0 & -B_x \\ -\frac{E_z}{c} & -B_y & B_x & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

The contraction $F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu}$ involves summing over all indices:

$$F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu} = \sum_{\mu,\nu} F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu}$$

To perform this contraction, we calculate the individual components:

$$F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu} = F_{01}F^{01} + F_{02}F^{02} + F_{03}F^{03} + F_{10}F^{10} + F_{12}F^{12} + F_{13}F^{13} + F_{20}F^{20} + F_{21}F^{21} + F_{23}F^{23} + F_{30}F^{30} + F_{31}F^{31} + F_{32}F^{32} \quad (41)$$

Computing these terms yields:

$$F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu} = 2 \left[\left(\frac{E_x^2}{c^2} + \frac{E_y^2}{c^2} + \frac{E_z^2}{c^2} \right) - (B_x^2 + B_y^2 + B_z^2) \right]$$

where $\mathbf{E}^2 = E_x^2 + E_y^2 + E_z^2$ is the squared magnitude of the electric field, and $\mathbf{B}^2 = B_x^2 + B_y^2 + B_z^2$ is the squared magnitude of the magnetic field. Simplifying the expression, we get:

$$F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu} = 2 \left(\frac{\mathbf{E}^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{B}^2 \right) \quad (42)$$

This expression represents an invariant quantity in electromagnetism, encapsulating the relationship between the electric and magnetic fields. Thus, $F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu}$ equals $2 \left(\frac{\mathbf{E}^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{B}^2 \right)$ in this metric convention.

Quod erat demonstrandum.

In other words, equation 40 becomes:

$${}_{\text{EM}}T = g^{\mu\nu}T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{4-D}{4} \right) \left(2 \left(\frac{\mathbf{E}^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{B}^2 \right) \right) \right) \quad (43)$$

In general, the trace of the stress-energy momentum tensor of the electromagnetic field is given as:

$${}_{\text{EM}}T = g^{\mu\nu}T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{2}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{4-D}{4} \right) \left(\left(\frac{\mathbf{E}^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{B}^2 \right) \right) \right) \quad (44)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

Implications for Different Dimensions

- **In $D = 4$ Dimensions:** The trace T is zero. This implies that in four-dimensional spacetime, the electromagnetic stress-energy tensor is traceless, which is related to scale and conformal invariance in four dimensions.
- **In $D \neq 4$ Dimensions:** The trace is generally non-zero. For dimensions other than four, the trace of the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field is not zero, indicating that the theory is only scale invariant and not conformally invariant.

Geometrization of the Stress-Energy Tensor of the Electromagnetic Field

In the exploration of geometrizing the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field, several key contributions have significantly shaped the discourse. Kibble (see [Kibble, 1961](#)) was pioneering in the attempt to reconcile electromagnetic theory with the geometric formulation of gravity. Misner et al. (see [Misner et al., 1973](#)) explored how various fields, including electromagnetism, could be described within the geometric framework of spacetime. Although the primary focus of Misner et al. was on gravity, their extensive discussion on the interactions between fields and spacetime curvature was crucial for setting the stage for a broader understanding of how electromagnetic fields might be integrated into general relativity. Contributions built upon the others, expanding the theoretical framework for integrating electromagnetism with general relativity. Penrose's (see [Penrose, 1984](#)) exploration of nonlinear field theories highlighted the complexities and possibilities of incorporating such fields into a geometric theory of gravity. These and other works paved the way for ongoing research in this complex and intriguing area of theoretical physics. Nonetheless, geometrizing the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field presents significant challenges primarily due to the nature of the stress-energy tensor and its interaction with the geometry of spacetime. In general relativity, the stress-energy tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$ represents the distribution of energy and momentum in spacetime, and its geometric interpretation is often linked to how matter and energy influence the curvature of spacetime. However, the electromagnetic field's stress-energy tensor, given by

$$T_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \right),$$

poses a unique challenge due to its dependence on both the field tensor $F_{\mu\nu}$ and the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$.

The core issue lies in the fact that the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field is derived from the variation of the electromagnetic action with respect to the metric. This tensor does not naturally fit into a framework where the field equations are derived purely from a geometric standpoint without invoking the dynamics of the field itself. Unlike matter fields, which can be described in terms of geometrical properties such as mass-energy density and pressure, the electromagnetic field is governed by its own dynamical equations, Maxwell's equations, which do not straightforwardly translate into a purely geometrical description. However, achieving success in geometrizing the electromagnetic stress-energy tensor could necessitate a novel and fundamentally different approach to incorporating electromagnetic field dynamics within the fabric of spacetime geometry. Such a success could potentially lead to a more unified theory where electromagnetism and gravitation are described by a single geometric framework, possibly leading to new insights into quantum gravity and the nature of spacetime itself. It might also offer a different perspective on unifying fundamental forces by suggesting new forms of gravitational theory or modifying our understanding of spacetime curvature. In fact, achieving this would require overcoming significant theoretical obstacles, including reconciling the field's dynamics with a purely geometrical description and ensuring consistency with established physical laws. The impact of such a breakthrough would be profound, potentially reshaping our understanding of fundamental interactions and leading to new theoretical developments in physics.

NUMERUS LEGIS NATURALIS: 4 (Geometrization of the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field). The stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field is geometrized as:

$$T_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \right) = b g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{{}_{\text{EM}}T}{D} g_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{2}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{4-D}{4D} \right) \left(\left(\frac{\mathbf{E}^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{B}^2 \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (45)$$

where:

- $F_{\mu\nu}$ is the electromagnetic field tensor.
- $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor.
- b is the scalar of the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field.
- ${}_{\text{EM}}T$ is the trace of of the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field.
- D is space-time dimension.
- μ_0 stands for the **permeability of free space** (also known as the **magnetic constant**). It is a fundamental physical constant that quantifies the ability of a vacuum to support a magnetic field. In the International System of Units (SI), μ_0 is defined as:

$$\mu_0 = 4\pi \times 10^{-7} \text{ N/A}^2$$

where N/A^2 denotes newtons per ampere squared. This constant is crucial in electromagnetism as it relates the magnetic field (B) to the magnetic force and is a key component in Maxwell's equations and in the definition of the speed of light in vacuum.

- $\mathbf{E}$ denotes the **electric field vector**. It is a vector quantity representing the force experienced by a unit positive charge placed in the field. The magnitude of $\mathbf{E}$ is the electric field strength, and it points in the direction of the force that a positive test charge would experience.
- $\mathbf{B}$ denotes the **magnetic field vector**. It is a vector quantity describing the force exerted on a moving charge or a magnetic dipole. The magnitude of $\mathbf{B}$ is the magnetic flux density or magnetic field strength, indicating the strength and direction of the magnetic field.
- c is the **speed of light in vacuum**, a fundamental constant of nature that appears as a normalization factor to ensure dimensional consistency, converting electric field units to match the magnetic field units.

Proof by Direct Proof. We begin this proof by acknowledging the validity of the fundamental identity:

$$1 = 1 \quad (46)$$

Multiplying equation 46 by the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field denoted as ${}_{\text{EM}}T_{\mu\nu}$ it is

$${}_{\text{EM}}T_{\mu\nu} = {}_{\text{EM}}T_{\mu\nu} \quad (47)$$

The the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field is determined as ${}_{\text{EM}}T_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} (F_{\mu\alpha}F_{\nu}{}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4}g_{\mu\nu}F_{\alpha\beta}F^{\alpha\beta}) = b_{\mu\nu}$. Equation 47 becomes:

$$T_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(F_{\mu\alpha}F_{\nu}{}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4}g_{\mu\nu}F_{\alpha\beta}F^{\alpha\beta} \right) \quad (48)$$

Taking the trace of the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field, we obtain (see equation 44):

$${}_{\text{EM}}T = g^{\mu\nu}T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{2}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{4-D}{4} \right) \left(\left(\frac{\mathbf{E}^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{B}^2 \right) \right) \right) \quad (49)$$

Multiplying equation 49 by $g_{\mu\nu}$, it is

$${}_{\text{EM}}T g_{\mu\nu} = g_{\mu\nu} g^{\mu\nu} T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{2}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{4-D}{4} \right) \left(\left(\frac{\mathbf{E}^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{B}^2 \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (50)$$

However, it is secured that $g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu} = D$, where D is space-time dimension. Equation 50 changes slightly and becomes:

$${}_{\text{EM}}T g_{\mu\nu} = D T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{2}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{4-D}{4} \right) \left(\left(\frac{\mathbf{E}^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{B}^2 \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (51)$$

In general, we define the scalar b of the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field as:

$$b = \frac{{}_{\text{EM}}T}{D} = \left(\frac{2}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{4-D}{4D} \right) \left(\left(\frac{\mathbf{E}^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{B}^2 \right) \right) \right) \quad (52)$$

The completely geometrized stress-energy momentum tensor of the electromagnetic field under conditions of D space-time dimensions is given as:

$$T_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(F_{\mu\alpha}F_{\nu}{}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4}g_{\mu\nu}F_{\alpha\beta}F^{\alpha\beta} \right) = b g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{{}_{\text{EM}}T}{D} g_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{2}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{4-D}{4D} \right) \left(\left(\frac{\mathbf{E}^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{B}^2 \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (53)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

The n th index, D-dimensional, completely geometrized stress-energy momentum tensor of the electromagnetic field is given as:

$$T_{\mu\nu\dots} = b g_{\mu\nu\dots} = \frac{{}_{\text{EM}}T}{D} g_{\mu\nu\dots} = \left(\frac{2}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{4-D}{4D} \right) \left(\left(\frac{\mathbf{E}^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{B}^2 \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu\dots} \quad (54)$$

The four basic fields of nature $a_{\mu\nu}$, $b_{\mu\nu}$, $c_{\mu\nu}$, $d_{\mu\nu}$

Under the conditions stipulated by equation 53, the derived relationship provide a comprehensive framework that elucidates how various variables might interact and influence each other, establishing a clear and consistent understanding of their interdependencies within the given context.

The geometrized stress-energy tensor of ordinary matter $a_{\mu\nu}$

The unification of the strong force and the weak force into something similar to the geometrized stress-energy tensor of ordinary matter $a_{\mu\nu}$ is possible. We obtain

Proof by Direct Proof.

$$a_{\mu\nu} = ag_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\left(\frac{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G \cdot T}{c^4 \cdot D} \right) - \left(\frac{2}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{4-D}{4D} \right) \left(\left(\frac{\mathbf{E}^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{B}^2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (55)$$

where T is Laue's (see also Laue, 1911) scalar (see also Einstein and Grossmann, 1913, p. 21).

Quod erat demonstrandum.

The tensor $b_{\mu\nu}$

The geometrized stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field, $b_{\mu\nu}$, is given as:

Proof by Direct Proof.

$$b_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \right) = bg_{\mu\nu} = \frac{EMT}{D} g_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{2}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{4-D}{4D} \right) \left(\left(\frac{\mathbf{E}^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{B}^2 \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (56)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

The tensor $c_{\mu\nu}$

The geometrized basic field of nature $c_{\mu\nu}$ is given as:

Proof by Direct Proof.

$$c_{\mu\nu} = cg_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{2}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{4-D}{4D} \right) \left(\left(\frac{\mathbf{E}^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{B}^2 \right) \right) \right) - (\Lambda) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (57)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

The tensor $d_{\mu\nu}$

The geometrized basic field of nature $d_{\mu\nu}$ is given as:

Proof by Direct Proof.

$$d_{\mu\nu} = dg_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - \left(\frac{2}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{4-D}{4D} \right) \left(\left(\frac{\mathbf{E}^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{B}^2 \right) \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (58)$$

where R is the Ricci scalar.

Quod erat demonstrandum.

The tensor $a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}$

The unified field $a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}$ is given as:

Proof by Direct Proof.

$$a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \right) + \left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - (\Lambda) \right) g_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - (\Lambda) \right) g_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (59)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

The tensor $a_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu}$

The unified field $a_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu}$ is given as:

Proof by Direct Proof.

$$a_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} - b_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \right) + (\Lambda) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - (Rg_{\mu\nu}) + (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (60)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

The tensor $b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu}$

The unification of gravitation and electromagnetism (see also Einstein, 1925) represents a profound historical goal in theoretical physics, as it could be of help to unify all fundamental forces of nature into a single coherent framework. Historically, Einstein's pursuit of such a unification, often referred to as Einstein's unified field theory program (see Sauer, 2015, pp. 237-260), encountered significant challenges. Einstein aimed to extend his theory of general relativity, which successfully describes gravitation, to incorporate electromagnetism within a unified geometric context. Despite Einstein's groundbreaking work on general relativity, Einstein's efforts to achieve such a fundamental breakthrough on this issue were ultimately in vain. The strategic importance of unifying gravitation and electromagnetism lies in its potential to offer a more complete understanding of the fundamental interactions of nature. A successful unification would not only simplify the description of physical phenomena but also potentially reveal deeper insights into the nature of spacetime and fundamental forces. By merging the curvature of spacetime with electromagnetic field dynamics, a unified theory could address questions about the interplay between gravity and electromagnetism, providing a more unified view of physical laws. Einstein's attempts were constrained by the limitations of his era's mathematical and conceptual tools. The development of quantum mechanics and modern field theories has since provided new approaches to addressing these challenges. Contemporary efforts, such as those involving string theory and quantum gravity, build upon Einstein's legacy by seeking to unify all fundamental forces, including the strong and weak nuclear forces alongside gravitation and electromagnetism. Thus, while Einstein's quest for a unified field theory did not achieve its goal, it laid the groundwork for subsequent theoretical advancements. The strategic pursuit of unification continues to drive research, with the hope that a successful theory will offer profound implications for our understanding of the universe and its fundamental laws. The unified field of gravitation and electromagnetism is given as:

$$b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} = b_{\mu\nu} + (b_{\mu\nu} - (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu})) = (b + c) g_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(2 \left(\frac{2}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{4-D}{4D} \right) \left(\frac{\mathbf{E}^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{B}^2 \right) \right) \right) - (\Lambda) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (61)$$

or more simplified

Proof by Direct Proof.

$$b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} = (b + c) g_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\left(\frac{4-D}{\mu_0 D} \right) \left(\frac{\mathbf{E}^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{B}^2 \right) \right) - (\Lambda) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (62)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

The tensor $a_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}$

The unified field $a_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}$ is given as:

Proof by Direct Proof.

$$a_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = (a + d) g_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - b_{\mu\nu} - c_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{4-D}{\mu_0 D} \right) \left(\frac{\mathbf{E}^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{B}^2 \right) \right) - (\Lambda) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (63)$$

where $R_{\mu\nu}$ is given (see Barukčić, 2022, pp. 28-32) as:

$$R_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{R}{D}\right)g_{\mu\nu} \quad (64)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

There is no need to rely on the cosmological constant $-\Lambda$. The same can be derived from the rearranged Einstein field equations

$$G_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}\right) = -(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (65)$$

and taking the trace:

$$G_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu}\right) = -(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu}) \quad (66)$$

We obtain

Proof by Direct Proof.

$$-\Lambda = \left(\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - \left(\frac{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G \cdot T}{c^4 \cdot D}\right)\right) \quad (67)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

The tensor $a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}$

The unified field $a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}$ is given as:

Proof by Direct Proof.

$$a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\left(\frac{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G \cdot T}{c^4 \cdot D}\right) - \left(\frac{2}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{4-D}{4D}\right) \left(\frac{\mathbf{E}^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{B}^2\right)\right)\right) + \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - (\Lambda)\right)g_{\mu\nu} \quad (68)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

The tensor $a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}$

The unified field $a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}$ is given as:

Proof by Direct Proof.

$$a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) + (\Lambda)\right) + \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - \left(\frac{2}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{4-D}{4D}\right) \left(\frac{\mathbf{E}^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{B}^2\right)\right)\right)\right)g_{\mu\nu} \quad (69)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

or more simply as:

$$a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) + (\Lambda) - \left(\frac{2}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{4-D}{4D} \right) \left(\left(\frac{\mathbf{E}^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{B}^2 \right) \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (70)$$

The tensor $b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}$

The unified field $b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}$ is given as:

Proof by Direct Proof.

$$b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} - a_{\mu\nu} - b_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{8\pi G T}{c^4 D} \right) \right) + \left(\frac{2}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{4-D}{4D} \right) \left(\left(\frac{\mathbf{E}^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{B}^2 \right) \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (71)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

It should be left to further research to determine whether the unified field $b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}$ can be considered as a tensor of non-locality (see Barukčić, 2020). The unification of additional fields is, under certain circumstances, a matter of personal preference.

The tensor $b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}$

The unified field $b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}$ is given as:

Proof by Direct Proof.

$$b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = b_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) + \left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - (\Lambda) \right) g_{\mu\nu} = Rg_{\mu\nu} - \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} \quad (72)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

The tensor $\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times (g_{\mu\nu}))$ is determined by tensor $c_{\mu\nu}$ and tensor $d_{\mu\nu}$

NUMERUS LEGIS NATURALIS: 5 (TENSOR OF NON-ENERGY). It is:

$$c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times (g_{\mu\nu})) \quad (73)$$

Proof by Direct Proof.

To begin with, we acknowledge a fundamental identity in tensor algebra:

$$1 = 1 \quad (74)$$

Next, we recognize that the Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ is given by:

$$R_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} \quad (75)$$

In our understanding, the Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ is determined by the four basic fields of nature denoted as $a_{\mu\nu}$, $b_{\mu\nu}$, $c_{\mu\nu}$ and $d_{\mu\nu}$. This allows us to consider the sum of various tensor components, which we assume to equal the Ricci tensor:

$$a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} \quad (76)$$

From the above equation, we can isolate $c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}$:

$$c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - a_{\mu\nu} - b_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - (a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu}) \quad (77)$$

Substituting equation 1 into equation 77, we have:

$$c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - \left(R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})\right) \quad (78)$$

Simplifying the above equation, we find:

$$c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - R_{\mu\nu} + \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (79)$$

Finally, this simplifies to:

$$c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (80)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

The following illustration is intended to further clarify equation 80.

From equation 80 follows that

$$d_{\mu\nu} = -(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) + \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - c_{\mu\nu} \quad (81)$$

Especially under conditions where

$$\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - c_{\mu\nu} = 0 \quad (82)$$

it is

$$d_{\mu\nu} = -(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (83)$$

and

$$c_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) \quad (84)$$

and equally

$$b_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (85)$$

and finally

$$a_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - (R \times g_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\frac{R}{D} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (R \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (86)$$

About the possibility of a common tensor $y_{\mu\nu}$

The question of whether two tensors, the Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ and the tensor $\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\Lambda \times (g_{\mu\nu})\right)$, should have something in common raises significant theoretical considerations about their nature and interrelationships. In general, if two tensors like the Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ and the tensor $\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\Lambda \times (g_{\mu\nu})\right)$ share a common property or component, such as a shared tensor $y_{\mu\nu}$, it often reflects an underlying connection or unity between both. In examining whether two tensors, the Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ and the tensor $\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\Lambda \times (g_{\mu\nu})\right)$, share a common component, it is important to recognize that accounting for all conceivable conditions and interrelations in objective reality might be beyond our capability. The complexities of the real world may not always be fully comprehensible. Therefore, it is both practical and necessary to base our analyses on specific assumptions, which should be clearly defined and distinguished from a purely scientific proof. For example, when considering whether there is a shared element between two tensors that initially appear independent, we need to evaluate the conditions under which such commonality could arise. If tensors, the Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ and the tensor $\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\Lambda \times (g_{\mu\nu})\right)$, belong to the same structural system or originate from a common source, it is plausible that they will exhibit shared components or characteristics. This shared feature arises naturally from their interconnected or systemic relationships. On the other hand, if the tensors are defined within entirely separate contexts or frameworks, the likelihood of finding a common component decreases. Investigating the presence of a common feature between entities that seem independent at first glance can reveal important insights into their underlying connections. Although predicting all possible conditions and interrelations is challenging, making specific assumptions allows us to explore and understand potential commonalities that may exist. Under which conditions do tensors like the Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ and the tensor $\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\Lambda \times (g_{\mu\nu})\right)$ share a common component, do both possess a common origin? In general, a kind of a unified field could be a possible origin of both tensors. In other words, the commonality the Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ and the tensor $\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\Lambda \times (g_{\mu\nu})\right)$ might arise naturally from their interdependence or shared framework. In this case, we would expect something like

$$y_{\mu\nu} = G_{\mu\nu} - x_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\Lambda \times (g_{\mu\nu})\right) - z_{\mu\nu} \quad (87)$$

Conversely, theoretically it is possible that both tensors, the Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ and the tensor $\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\Lambda \times (g_{\mu\nu})\right)$, operate in entirely distinct contexts or frameworks and might not share any common element. In other words, both tensors defined in mutually exclusive manifolds or addressing different aspects of objective reality, the likelihood of a shared component diminishes. Furthermore, the absence of commonality can also occur if the entities are fundamentally different in their defining characteristics. In this case we would expect something like

$$y_{\mu\nu} = G_{\mu\nu} - x_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\Lambda \times (g_{\mu\nu})\right) - z_{\mu\nu} = 0 \quad (88)$$

Under these circumstances, it is

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - x_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\Lambda \times (g_{\mu\nu})\right) - z_{\mu\nu} \quad (89)$$

or

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times (g_{\mu\nu})) = x_{\mu\nu} - z_{\mu\nu} \quad (90)$$

Therefore, we cannot exclude that the presence of a common tensor between the two tensors, the Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ and the tensor $\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times (g_{\mu\nu}))$, might depend on their contextual or structural relationships. Nonetheless, from the pure visual inspection, it is evident that the Einstein tensor

$$G_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{\mathbf{R}}{2} \times \mathbf{g}_{\mu\nu}\right) \quad (91)$$

and the tensor

$$\underline{E}_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{\mathbf{R}}{2} \times \mathbf{g}_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (92)$$

appear to share a common component. The presence of the tensor $\left(\frac{\mathbf{R}}{2} \times \mathbf{g}_{\mu\nu}\right)$ in both tensors reveals an intrinsic and fundamental relationship between them. This tensor, even if appearing with opposite signs in each tensor, underscores a deep-seated connection and suggests that both tensors are not merely independent entities but are inherently linked through unknown common component. This fundamental overlap points to a significant structural or conceptual unity between the tensors, hinting at an underlying principle or mechanism that binds them together. Such a shared and unknown tensor implies that the tensors are part of a cohesive framework or system where their interactions and differences are governed by their mutual components. Thus, the presence of the common tensor

$$\left(\frac{\mathbf{R}}{2} \times \mathbf{g}_{\mu\nu}\right) \quad (93)$$

strongly suggests a more profound and fundamental relationship between the Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ and the tensor $\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times (g_{\mu\nu}))$ beyond superficial differences. Finally, the relationship between the Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ and the tensor $\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times (g_{\mu\nu}))$ is characterized by the presence of an unknown, shared tensor $y_{\mu\nu}$, as illustrated by the next figure. This inquiry into commonality should provide us with deeper insights into their interconnections and help us to understand the broader implications of their relationship.

The decomposition of the tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$

NUMERUS LEGIS NATURALIS: 6. Let $G_{\mu\nu}$ be a tensor, and let $y_{\mu\nu}$ and $a_{\mu\nu}$ be tensors such that the following equation holds:

$$G_{\mu\nu} = y_{\mu\nu} + a_{\mu\nu}.$$

We will show that this equation is valid under certain conditions.

Proof by Direct Proof. Step 1: Start with Identity

$$1 = 1. \tag{94}$$

Step 2: Assume Tensor Identity

$$G_{\mu\nu} = G_{\mu\nu}. \tag{95}$$

Step 3: Manipulate the Tensor Equation Subtract and add $a_{\mu\nu}$ to $G_{\mu\nu}$:

$$G_{\mu\nu} - a_{\mu\nu} + a_{\mu\nu} = G_{\mu\nu} \tag{96}$$

Step 4: Define a New Tensor Define a new tensor $y_{\mu\nu}$ such that:

$$y_{\mu\nu} = G_{\mu\nu} - a_{\mu\nu} \tag{97}$$

Substituting this definition into the equation, we get:

$$G_{\mu\nu} = y_{\mu\nu} + a_{\mu\nu} \tag{98}$$

Step 5: Verify Conditions The relationship $G_{\mu\nu} = y_{\mu\nu} + a_{\mu\nu}$ is valid if $y_{\mu\nu}$ and $a_{\mu\nu}$ are defined as stated and if the tensor arithmetic operations are valid within the context of the tensors involved.

Quod erat demonstrandum.

The preceding proof establishes that the Einstein tensor

$$G_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} + y_{\mu\nu} \tag{99}$$

can be expressed as the sum of two distinct tensors, $y_{\mu\nu}$ and $a_{\mu\nu}$. This result shows that $y_{\mu\nu}$ and $a_{\mu\nu}$ together reconstruct the original Einstein tensor, enabling separate analysis of its components. By defining $y_{\mu\nu}$ as

$$y_{\mu\nu} = G_{\mu\nu} - a_{\mu\nu} \tag{100}$$

we gain insight into how the tensor $a_{\mu\nu}$ contributes to the overall structure of the tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$. The proof ensures that this decomposition is mathematically sound within tensor operations. Such a separation is useful for simplifying complex tensor equations or focusing on specific contributions in the tensor framework.

The decomposition of the tensor $\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$

NUMERUS LEGIS NATURALIS: 7. Let $\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$ be a tensor, and let $y_{\mu\nu}$ and $d_{\mu\nu}$ be tensors then the following equation holds:

$$\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = y_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} \quad (101)$$

Now, we will show that this equation is valid in general.

Proof by Direct Proof. Step 1: Start with Identity

$$1 = 1. \quad (102)$$

Step 2: Assume Tensor Identity

$$\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (103)$$

Step 3: Manipulate the Tensor Equation Subtract and add $d_{\mu\nu}$ to $\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$:

$$\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) + 0 = \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) - d_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (104)$$

Step 4: Define a New Tensor Define a new tensor $y_{\mu\nu}$ such that:

$$y_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) - d_{\mu\nu}. \quad (105)$$

Substituting this definition into the equation, we get:

$$\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = y_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} \quad (106)$$

Step 5: Verify Conditions The relationship $\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = y_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}$ is valid if $y_{\mu\nu}$ and $d_{\mu\nu}$ are defined as stated and if the tensor arithmetic operations are valid within the context of the tensors involved.

Quod erat demonstrandum.

The proof before demonstrates that the tensor

$$\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (107)$$

can be decomposed into two distinct tensors, $y_{\mu\nu}$ and $d_{\mu\nu}$. This decomposition implies that $y_{\mu\nu}$ and $d_{\mu\nu}$ together reconstruct the original tensor, thus providing a method to analyze the components of the tensor separately. By defining $y_{\mu\nu}$ as

$$y_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) - d_{\mu\nu} \quad (108)$$

we can examine the properties and implications of $d_{\mu\nu}$ in relation to the overall tensor structure. The proof also confirms too, that this separation is mathematically consistent under tensor arithmetic. This decomposition of the tensor is beneficial for simplifying complex tensor equations or isolating specific contributions within a broader tensor framework. The results obtained so far are illustrated in more detail in the following diagram.

The question of why there should be a common component, such as $y_{\mu\nu}$, between the tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ and the expression $\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}$ remains no longer unresolved. We have slight evidence that there might be an inherent shared structure or interaction within these tensors that requires further examination. Specifically, understanding why $y_{\mu\nu}$ is a common element might provide insights into the relationships between different tensors and how they can be decomposed or analyzed. Addressing this far reaching question will invite deeper investigation into the mathematical relationships and physical implications of these tensors. Clarifying this aspect could elucidate the role of $y_{\mu\nu}$ in connecting or bridging different tensor formulations.

The tensor $\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right)$ is determined by tensor $c_{\mu\nu}$ and tensor $d_{\mu\nu}$

NUMERUS LEGIS NATURALIS: 8. The tensor $\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right)$ is determined by the two basic fields of nature $b_{\mu\nu}$ and $d_{\mu\nu}$ as:

$$b_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) \quad (109)$$

We will show that this equation is valid in general.

Proof by Direct Proof. Step 1: Start with Identity

$$1 = 1. \quad (110)$$

Step 2: Assume Tensor Identity

$$y_{\mu\nu} = y_{\mu\nu} \quad (111)$$

Step 3: Manipulate this Tensor Equation

According to equation 100, it is $y_{\mu\nu} = G_{\mu\nu} - a_{\mu\nu}$. We rearrange equation 111 to obtain:

$$G_{\mu\nu} - a_{\mu\nu} = y_{\mu\nu}. \quad (112)$$

According to equation 108, it is $y_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) - d_{\mu\nu}$. We rearrange equation 112 to obtain:

$$G_{\mu\nu} - a_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) - d_{\mu\nu} \quad (113)$$

Rearranging equation 113, it is

$$G_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = a_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu} \quad (114)$$

Simplifying, it is

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})\right) = a_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu} \quad (115)$$

The Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ is determined by the for basic fields of nature (see equation 76). We obtain

$$\left(a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}) = a_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu} \quad (116)$$

Simplifying equation 116, it is

$$(+b_{\mu\nu}) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) = -d_{\mu\nu} \quad (117)$$

In general, the tensor $\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right)$ is determined as

$$b_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) \quad (118)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

The following gives an optical overview of equation 80.

Einstein's tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ is determined by tensor $a_{\mu\nu}$ and tensor $c_{\mu\nu}$

NUMERUS LEGIS NATURALIS: 9. The Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ is determined by the two basic fields of nature $a_{\mu\nu}$ and $c_{\mu\nu}$ as

$$G_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} \quad (119)$$

Proof by Direct Proof. We begin by acknowledging the identity:

$$1 = 1 \quad (120)$$

and

$$R_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} \quad (121)$$

It is $a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu}$. Equation 121 becomes:

$$a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} \quad (122)$$

Rearranging equation 122, it is

$$a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - b_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu} \quad (123)$$

Based on equation 118, it is $b_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right)$. Equation 123 becomes:

$$a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) \quad (124)$$

In general, the Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ is determined the two basic fields of nature, denoted as $a_{\mu\nu}$ and $c_{\mu\nu}$ and given as

$$a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} = G_{\mu\nu} \quad (125)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

The following illustration is intended to further clarify equation 125 in more detail.

The unknown tensor $y_{\mu\nu}$ becomes known

In our everyday hunt for the truth, the method of advancing from the known and secure to the unknown and uncertain can sometimes be an appropriate approach to knowledge acquisition. This method begins with established and verifiable knowledge—what we already understand and can confirm with certainty. By starting from these solid grounds, can help authors to develop a structured framework that guides exploration into less familiar territories. Such a progression involves identifying and leveraging existing knowledge as a stepping stone for uncovering new insights. In general, moving from known to unknown is inherently systematic; it employs logical reasoning and empirical evidence to bridge gaps in understanding. By systematically questioning and expanding upon established concepts, authors might be able to explore the implications and boundaries of current knowledge. Equally, acknowledging and addressing uncertainties as they arise might be possible. This iterative approach involves refining hypotheses and theories based on new data or perspectives. Through rigorous examination and adjustment, scientist can progressively build upon the foundation of established knowledge. Thus, moving from known to unknown fosters a dynamic and iterative exploration of objective reality. It ensures that new insights are grounded in a reliable context while continually pushing the boundaries of what is known. Such an approach not only enriches scientific discourse but also contributes to broader intellectual progress.

NUMERUS LEGIS NATURALIS: 10 (THE UNKNOWN TENSOR $y_{\mu\nu}$ BECOMES KNOWN). The unknown tensor $y_{\mu\nu}$ is identified as

$$y_{\mu\nu} = c_{\mu\nu} \quad (126)$$

Proof by Direct Proof. We begin this proof by acknowledging the validity of the fundamental identity:

$$1 = 1 \quad (127)$$

Multiplying equation 127 by $G_{\mu\nu}$ it is

$$G_{\mu\nu} = G_{\mu\nu} \quad (128)$$

Meanwhile, we have been able to recognise that the Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ is determined the two basic fields of nature $a_{\mu\nu}$ and $c_{\mu\nu}$ as $G_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu}$ (see equation 125). Equation 128 becomes

$$G_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} \quad (129)$$

In the same context, it was possible to decompose the Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ as $G_{\mu\nu} = y_{\mu\nu} + a_{\mu\nu}$ (see equation 98). Equation 129 becomes

$$y_{\mu\nu} + a_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} \quad (130)$$

In general, the unknown tensor as $y_{\mu\nu}$ becomes known as

$$y_{\mu\nu} = c_{\mu\nu} \quad (131)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

The relationship between the tensor $b_{\mu\nu}$ and the tensor $c_{\mu\nu}$

NUMERUS LEGIS NATURALIS: 11. The relationship between the tensor $b_{\mu\nu}$ and the tensor $c_{\mu\nu}$ is given by:

$$c_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = b_{\mu\nu}. \quad (132)$$

Proof by Direct Proof. We start by reaffirming the fundamental identity:

$$1 = 1. \quad (133)$$

Multiplying both sides of equation 133 by the stress-energy tensor of matter: $\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}$, we obtain:

$$\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \quad (134)$$

In general, the Einstein field equations are given by:

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \quad (135)$$

Rewriting and decomposing (see equation 1) this equation, we get:

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} \quad (136)$$

We can simplify this to:

$$G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} \quad (137)$$

We know from previous results (see equation 125) that: $G_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu}$. Substituting this into equation 137, we obtain:

$$a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu}. \quad (138)$$

Thus, the relationship between the tensor $c_{\mu\nu}$ and the tensor $b_{\mu\nu}$ is given by:

$$c_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = b_{\mu\nu}. \quad (139)$$

where $b_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor of electromagnetism.

Quod erat demonstrandum.

The unity and the opposition between gravitation and electromagnetism is given as

$$b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} = c_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (140)$$

Black holes and electromagnetism

While reflecting on the current investigation, it's essential to recognize the milestones we've achieved up to this point in understanding the fundamental forces which might govern objective reality. By identifying the four fundamental fields of nature, we establish a solid foundation that allows for the precise and profound scientific analysis of various phenomena in objective reality, including black holes, wormholes, and quantum gravity et cetera. This foundational understanding allows us to approach these complex topics with a clearer perspective. Thus far, given the wealth of new insights, it's essential not to overlook the progress we've made so far. By briefly revisiting these advancements through a visual lens, we can maintain clarity and ensure that our understanding remains comprehensive as we move forward. Therefore, before we turn to the actual issue of the relationship between a black hole and electromagnetism, it's valuable to take a step back and visually reflect on these advancements in greater detail. Table 2 provides an optical overview of the four basic fields of nature (Barukčić, 2016c,b) identified so far.

		Curvature		
		YES	NO	
Momentum	YES	$a_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} - \frac{R}{2} + \Lambda \right) - \left(\frac{2}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{4-D}{4D} \right) \left(\frac{E^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{B}^2 \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu}$	$b_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{2}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{4-D}{4D} \right) \left(\frac{E^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{B}^2 \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu}$	$\underbrace{\left(\frac{R}{D} - \frac{R}{2} + \Lambda \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \times g_{\mu\nu}}_{\text{The Einstein's field equations}}$
	NO	$c_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\left(\frac{2}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{4-D}{4D} \right) \left(\frac{E^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{B}^2 \right) \right) - \Lambda \right) g_{\mu\nu}$	$d_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{2} - \left(\frac{2}{\mu_0} \left(\frac{4-D}{4D} \right) \left(\frac{E^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{B}^2 \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu}$	$\left(\frac{R}{2} - \Lambda \right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$
		$G_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} - \frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$	$\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}$	$R_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{R}{D} \times g_{\mu\nu}$

Table 2. Scalars, the Einstein's field equations and the four basic fields of nature

The essential groundwork and foundations for further progress is established by now. What consequences might arise from this for our understanding of black holes? Black holes come in several well-known forms, each characterized by different properties. The **Schwarzschild black hole** (see Schwarzschild, 1916), the simplest type, is a non-rotating black hole with no electric charge, formed from the collapse of a massive star. The **Reissner-Nordström black hole** (see Reissner, 1916; Nordström, 1918) is charged, leading to the inclusion of an additional term in the equations to account for electrostatic forces. The **Kerr black hole** (see Kerr, 1963) represents a rotating black hole and introduces the concept of angular momentum, featuring an ergosphere due to its rotation. Finally, the **Kerr-Newman black hole** (see Kerr and Newman, 1963) combines rotation and electric charge, encompassing the most general solution for a black hole with both angular momentum and charge. More or less, black holes, characterized by their immense gravitational pull, are regions where the gravitational field is so intense that no electromagnetic radiation can escape from the interior of such a black hole. However, some theories introduces the concept of Hawking radiation (see Hawking, 1974), predicting that an event horizons itself might emit some electromagnetic radiation which could be detected outside the event horizon. Nonetheless, it is important to note that a black hole is characterized by the fact that no electromagnetic radiation can escape from it. Consequently, under these circumstances, **per definitionem**, the event horizon itself cannot be considered a part of the black hole

in terms of its ability to emit some electromagnetic radiation. This characteristic reinforces the possibility that the event horizon acts as a boundary of a black hole beyond which no electromagnetic radiation can return back to an external observer. Therefore, any analysis or measurement of electromagnetic radiation related to a black hole must be confined to the region outside the event horizon, where such radiation could theoretically be detected or studied. Inside the event horizon, the absence of escaping electromagnetic radiation further emphasizes the isolation of the black hole's core, which remains fundamentally opaque and detectable at least through gravitational effects and indirect observations.

NUMERUS LEGIS NATURALIS: 12 (BLACK HOLES AND ELECTROMAGNETISM). Black holes exclude electromagnetism. It is

$$c_{\mu\nu} = -(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (141)$$

Proof by Direct Proof. We start by reaffirming the fundamental identity:

$$1 = 1. \quad (142)$$

Multiplying both sides of equation 133 by the stress-energy tensor of matter: $\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}$, we obtain:

$$\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \quad (143)$$

In general, the Einstein field equations are given by:

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \quad (144)$$

Rewriting and decomposing (see equation 1) this equation, we get:

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} \quad (145)$$

Vranceanu(Vranceanu, 1936) is elaborating on the same issue too. The energy tensor T_{kl} is treated by Vranceanu as the sum of two tensors one of which is due to the electromagnetic field ($b_{\mu\nu}$).

“On peut aussi supposer que le tenseur d'énergie T_{kl} soit la somme de deux tenseurs dont un dû au champ électromagnétique . . .”(Vranceanu, 1936)

In English: ‘One can also assume that the energy tensor T_{kl} be the sum of two tensors one of which is due to the electromagnetic field.’ We can simplify this to:

$$G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} \quad (146)$$

We know from previous results (see equation 125) that: $G_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu}$. Substituting this into equation 146, we obtain:

$$a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu}. \quad (147)$$

Thus, the relationship between the tensor $c_{\mu\nu}$ and the tensor $b_{\mu\nu}$ is given by:

$$c_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = b_{\mu\nu}. \quad (148)$$

where $b_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor of electromagnetism. Notably, black holes do not emit any electromagnetic radiation, which implies that the stress-energy tensor associated with electromagnetic fields, $b_{\mu\nu}$, outside a black hole vanishes. Inside a black hole, electromagnetic radiation might exist or not, the extreme gravitation of a black hole causes electromagnetic radiation not to leave the black hole itself. Consequently, the absence of detectable electromagnetic radiation implies that any electromagnetic stress-energy components outside a black hole which are caused by the black hole itself are effectively zero. This important feature of black holes simplifies our understanding of black holes by focusing solely on the gravitational effects and quantum phenomena that occur within their boundaries, thereby refining models of their behavior and interactions with the surrounding regions. Therefore, under conditions where $b_{\mu\nu} = 0$, we obtain

$$c_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = 0 \quad (149)$$

and at the end:

$$c_{\mu\nu} = -(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (150)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

In general, equation 150 can be illustrated as follows:

$R_{\mu\nu}$

while we consider circumstances where $\frac{R}{2}g_{\mu\nu} = 0$ (see also table 2). In other words, under these assumptions, the black hole should be viewed as everything except $-\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}$ or as **Black hole** = $R_{\mu\nu} - \Lambda g_{\mu\nu}$ which corresponds as such to dark matter (see Barukčić, 2025, p. 8). Under these circumstances, the black hole emerges as a natural prototype for dark matter.

4. Discussion

We have substantial grounds to propose that the gravitational field of a black hole is exclusively described by the term $-\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}$, where Λ represents a non-zero cosmological constant.

However, under conditions where the gravitational field is entirely determined by the cosmological constant $-\Lambda$, it profoundly influences the geometry and curvature of spacetime. In this scenario, the Einstein field equations

$$G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \right) \quad (151)$$

simplify to:

$$G_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \right) = -(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (152)$$

where $G_{\mu\nu}$ is the Einstein tensor, and $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor of spacetime. The effect of a negative non-zero cosmological constant $-\Lambda$ introduces significant effects of $-\Lambda$ on spacetime geometry. In point of fact, equation 152 in conjunction with equation 150 leads to significant doubts regarding the constancy of the cosmological constant Λ . A negative cosmological constant ($\Lambda < 0$) corresponds to an anti-de Sitter manifold. In this case, spacetime exhibits negative curvature, leading to a decelerating expansion. The anti-de Sitter space is characterized by a saddle-shaped geometry, which can have implications for the formation and stability of black holes.

Anti-de Sitter space (see [de Sitter, 1917](#)) is named after Willem de Sitter (1872–1934), which generalises to any number of space dimensions. In Anti-de Sitter space, as with de Sitter space, the curvature of spacetime is directly linked to the cosmological constant. Anti-de Sitter space is a highly symmetric, n-dimensional Lorentzian manifold, a space devoid of matter or energy, the curvature of spacelike sections is consistently negative, reflecting a hyperbolic geometry. The presence of $-\Lambda$ determines negative curvature of spacetime around a black hole and causes spacetime not to expand. However, this can lead to different boundary conditions and influence the thermodynamics and possible thermodynamic stability of black holes. In particular, the presence of a negative cosmological constant appears to allow the existence of a horizon structure which resembles a thermal or Hawking radiation-like boundary condition.

Often, Black holes are described by only three parameters: mass, charge, and angular momentum, suggesting that black holes lack other distinguishing features. A large amount of mass is being compressed into a very small space, leading to what is generally claimed as a **singularity** at its core—a point where, as it is claimed, the laws of physics as we currently understand them break down. The extreme gravitational pull of a black hole is so strong that nothing, not even light, can escape from it. The interior of a black hole remains one of the most mysterious and challenging areas in modern physics. The exact nature of the interior of a black hole remains an active area of research, with various theoretical models being proposed to address the unknowns, especially the nature of the singularity and the possible reconciliation of general relativity with quantum mechanics.

In the meantime, we have strong reasons to believe that black holes serve as a prototype for dark matter (see Barukčić, 2025, p. 8), which itself can be well-described by the equation $\text{Black hole} = R_{\mu\nu} - \Lambda g_{\mu\nu}$. This equation (see equation 59) also arises from a unified treatment of individual fields, as follows:

$$R_{\mu\nu} - (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\frac{R}{D} - \Lambda\right) g_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) + \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - \Lambda\right) g_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} \quad (153)$$

However, the results of this investigation reinforce our belief that equation 153 or $\left(\frac{R}{D} - \Lambda\right) g_{\mu\nu}$ describes the interior of a black hole very precisely. Based on the purely hypothetical and preliminary assumption that the logic presented here proves to be correct in further research, equation 153 would provide researchers with a highly precise mathematical tool to closely examine the internal events and structure within a black hole itself. We seem to be faced with the possibility of shedding some epistemological light on the darkness of the interior of black hole. As an example, we will consider the Schwarzschild metric. The Schwarzschild metric (see Schwarzschild, 1916), which describes the spacetime geometry surrounding a non-rotating, uncharged black hole, is given by:

$$ds^2 = -\left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right) c^2 dt^2 + \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right)^{-1} dr^2 + r^2 d\theta^2 + r^2 \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2 \quad (154)$$

where:

- G is the gravitational constant,
- M is the mass of the black hole,
- c is the speed of light,
- r , θ , and ϕ are the spherical coordinates,
- t is the time coordinate.

Under these assumptions, the interior of the **Schwarzschild black hole**, is determined in detail as

$$a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{R}{D} - \Lambda\right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (155)$$

where $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor of the Schwarzschild black hole.

5. Conclusion

A negative non-zero cosmological constant $-\Lambda$ appears to be the most determining factor of the spacetime geometry around a black hole.

Reason for Version III

- 1) Page 29: Omission of one unified field.
- 2) Page 42: Visual adjustments made in Table 2.
- 3) Page 44: Added figure.
- 4) Minimized the use of the word “theorem” throughout the article.

Erratum: August 17, 2024, version III

- 1) Page 15: Word “objective” changed to “nature”
- 2) Page 29: Misprint corrected in Equation 69.

Reason for Version IV

- 1) Page 26: Omission of other unified fields.
- 2) Page 27: Equation 61 improved.

Erratum II: August 17, 2024, version IV

Persistent, superficial, and entirely unnecessary misprints persist. The underlying cause is the lack of third-party review.

- 1) Page 29: Misprint corrected in Equation 71. Minus sign was used instead of plus sign.

Reason for Version V

1) Pages 45-46: Expanded the discussion to explore the implications of equation (see equation 59) in greater depth.

Acknowledgments

No funding or any financial support by a third party was received.

References

- Ilija Barukčić. Einstein's field equations and non-locality. *International Journal of Mathematics Trends and Technology IJMTT*, 66(6): 146–167, 2020. doi: 10.14445/22315373/IJMTT-V66I6P515. [IJMTT](#).
- Ilija Barukčić. Dark matter and dark energy. *Causation*, 20(4):91–114, 2025. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10719321. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10719321>. [Zenodo](#).
- Ilija Barukčić. Anti Einstein – Refutation of Einstein's General Theory of Relativity. *International Journal of Applied Physics and Mathematics*, 5(1):18–28, 2015a. ISSN 2010362X. doi: 10.17706/ijapm.2015.5.1.18-28.
- Ilija Barukčić. Anti Newton — Refutation of the Constancy of Newton's Gravitational Constant Big G. *International Journal of Applied Physics and Mathematics*, 5(2):126–136, 2015b. doi: 10.17706/ijapm.2015.5.2.126-136.
- Ilija Barukčić. Newton's Gravitational Constant Big G Is Not a Constant. *Journal of Modern Physics*, 7(66):510–522, 3 2016a. doi: 10.4236/jmp.2016.76053.
- Ilija Barukčić. The geometrization of the electromagnetic field. *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Physics*, 4(1212):2135–2171, 12 2016b. doi: 10.4236/jamp.2016.412211.
- Ilija Barukčić. Unified field theory. *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Physics*, 4(88):1379–1438, 8 2016c. doi: 10.4236/jamp.2016.48147.
- Ilija Barukčić. Time and gravitational field. *Causation*, 18(4):5–134, September 2022. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7281862. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7281862>. [Zenodo Version 20 ISBN 978-375-6843-30-5 Books on Demand, Norderstedt Zenodo All Versions](#).
- Charles Thomas Bolton. Identification of cygnus x-1 with hde 226868. *Nature*, 235(5336):271–273, 1972.
- Jocelyn Bell Burnell. Observations of a rapidly pulsating radio source. *Nature*, 217:709–710, 1967.
- Willem de Sitter. On the curvature of space. In *Proceedings of the Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie van Wetenschappen*, volume 20, pages 229–243, 1917.
- Albert Einstein. Die Grundlage der allgemeinen Relativitätstheorie. *Annalen der Physik*, 354(7):769–822, 1916. ISSN 1521-3889. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/andp.19163540702>. [Wiley online library](#).
- Albert Einstein. Kosmologische Betrachtungen zur allgemeinen Relativitätstheorie. *Sitzungsberichte der Königlich Preussischen Akademie der Wissenschaften (Berlin)*, page 142–152, 1917. [ECHO](#).
- Albert Einstein. *The meaning of relativity. Four lectures delivered at Princeton University, May, 1921*. Princeton University Press, Princeton, 1923.
- Albert Einstein. Einheitliche Feldtheorie von Gravitation und Elektrizität. *Preussische Akademie der Wissenschaften, Phys.-math. Klasse, Sitzungsberichte*, pages 414–419, 1925. doi: 10.1002/3527608958.ch30. URL <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1002/3527608958.ch30>.
- Albert Einstein and Marcel Grossmann. *Entwurf einer verallgemeinerten Relativitätstheorie und einer Theorie der Gravitation. I. Physikalischer Teil von Albert Einstein. II. Mathematischer Teil von Marcel Großmann*. Verlag von BG Teubner, Leipzig, September 1913. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7092832. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7092832>. [Zenodo](#).
- David Finkelstein. Past-future asymmetry of the gravitational field of a point mass. *Physical Review*, 110:965–967, 1958.
- Howard Georgi and Sheldon Glashow. Unity of all elementary-particle forces. *Physical Review Letters*, 32(8):438–441, 1974.
- Sheldon L. Glashow. The state of gauge theories. *Scientific American*, 223(3):92–102, 1970.
- Thomas L. Hankins. Pierre simon laplace, 1749–1827: A determined scientist (book review). *Physics Today*, 59(9):62–64, 2006. doi: 10.1063/1.2364251.

- Stephen W. Hawking. Black hole explosions? *Nature*, 248(5443):30–31, 1974. doi: 10.1038/248030a0.
- Roy P. Kerr. Gravitational field of a rotating black hole. *Physical Review Letters*, 11(5):237–238, 1963.
- Roy P. Kerr and Ezra T. Newman. Solutions of the einstein-maxwell equations. *Physical Review Letters*, 11(5):237–238, 1963.
- T. W. B. Kibble. Geometrization of the electromagnetic field. *Journal of Mathematical Physics*, 2(4):212–221, 1961. doi: 10.1063/1.1703727.
- Pierre-Simon Laplace. Exposition du système du monde, vol. ii. *De l’Imprimerie du Cercle Social Paris*, 1796.
- Pierre-Simon Laplace. Beweis des Satzes, dass die anziehende Kraft bey einem Weltkörper so groß seyn könne, dass das Licht davon nicht ausströmen kann. *Allgemeine Geographische Ephemeriden*, 4(1):1–6, July 1799.
- Joseph Larmor. A dynamical theory of the electric and luminiferous medium, part iii. relations with material media. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series A, Containing Papers of a Mathematical or Physical Character*, A195:1–77, 1900. doi: 10.1098/rsta.1900.0021.
- Max Laue. Über die relativität der strahlung. *Annalen der Physik*, 340:167–174, 1911. URL <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/andp.19113400304>.
- James Clerk Maxwell. A dynamical theory of the electromagnetic field. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London*, 155:459–512, 1865. doi: 10.1098/rstl.1865.0008.
- John Michell. VII. on the means of discovering the distance, magnitude, &c. of the fixed stars, in consequence of the diminution of the velocity of their light, in case such a diminution should be found to take place in any of them, and such other data should be procured from observations, as would be farther necessary for that purpose. by the rev. john michell, b.d. f.r.s. in a letter to henry cavendish, esq. f.r.s. and a.s. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London*, 74:35–57, 1784. [Royal Society](#).
- Charles W. Misner, Kip S. Thorne, and John Archibald Wheeler. *Gravitation*. W. H. Freeman, 1973. ISBN 978-0-7167-0334-1.
- Tomáš Málek. *General Relativity in Higher Dimensions*. PhD thesis, Institute of Theoretical Physics. Faculty of Mathematics and Physics. Charles University, Prague, 2012. URL <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1204.0291.pdf>.
- Gunnar Nordström. On the energy of the gravitational field of a point charge in einstein’s theory. *Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie van Wetenschappen Proceedings*, 20:1238–1244, 1918.
- R. Penrose. Nonlinear graviton theories. *General Relativity and Gravitation*, 16(10):965–975, 1984. doi: 10.1007/BF00756441.
- Hans Reissner. Über die eigengravitation des elektrischen feldes nach der einsteinschen theorie. *Annalen der Physik*, 50:106–120, 1916.
- Gregorio Ricci-Curbastro and Tullio Levi-Civita. Méthodes de calcul différentiel absolu et leurs applications. *Mathematische Annalen*, 54(1):125–201, 3 1900. ISSN 1432-1807. doi: 10.1007/BF01454201.
- Abdus Salam. Gauge unification of fundamental forces. *Physics Reports*, 49(4):303–322, 1979.
- Tilman Sauer. Einstein’s unified field theory program. In Michele Janssen and Christoph Lehner, editors, *The Cambridge Companion to Einstein*, pages 237–260. Cambridge University Press, 2015.
- Karl Schwarzschild. Über das gravitationsfeld eines massenpunktes nach der einstein’schen theorie. *Sitzungsberichte der Königlich Preußischen Akademie der Wissenschaften zu Berlin*, pages 189–196, 1916. In German.
- G. Vranceanu. Sur une théorie unitaire non holonome des champs physiques. *Journal de Physique et le Radium*, 7(12):514–526, 1936. ISSN 0368-3842. doi: 10.1051/jphysrad:01936007012051400. URL <http://www.edpsciences.org/10.1051/jphysrad:01936007012051400>.
- B Louise Webster and Paul Murdin. Cygnus x-1—a spectroscopic binary with a heavy companion? *Nature*, 235(5332):37–38, 1972.
- Steven Weinberg. A model of leptons. *Physical Review Letters*, 19(21):1264–1266, 1977.

Associated Data

Copyright

Copyright © August 18, 2024 by Ilija Barukčić, Horandstrasse, Jever, Germany. All Rights Reserved. Alle Rechte vorbehalten.

© 2025 Ilija Barukčić^{a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i, j, k, l, m} Chief-Editor, Jever, Germany, August 18, 2024. All rights reserved. Alle Rechte vorbehalten. This is an open access article which can be downloaded under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>).

I was born on October 1st, 1980, in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, which was formerly part of Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian descent. From 1982 to 1989, I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany, and currently work as a specialist in internal medicine.

Since my high school days at Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal in Baden-Württemberg, Germany, my primary field of research has been the mathematization of causal relationships. My interest encompasses a wide range of domains, including classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, and the theories of special and general relativity, as well as human medicine. My goal is to explore these fields to determine how they impact or challenge **the general validity of the principle of causality.**

^a<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6988-2780>

^b<https://www.webofscience.com/wos/author/record/1972920>

^c<https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=37099674500>

^d<https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=54974181600>

^e<https://www.mendeley.com/search/?authorFullName=Ilija%20Baruk%C4%8Di%C4%87&page=1&query=Barukcic&sortBy=relevance>

^f<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Ilija-Barukcic-2>

^g<https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=keywords:%22Baruk%C4%8Di%C4%87%22&sort=mostviewed>

^h<https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=keywords:%22Baruk%C4%8Di%C4%87,%20Conference%22>

ⁱ<https://twitter.com/ilijabarukcic?lang=de>

^jhttps://twitter.com/Causation_Journ

^khttps://vixra.org/author/ilija_barukcic

^l<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCwf3w1IngcukIOjpw8HTwg>

^m<https://portal.dnb.de/opac/showNextResultSite?currentResultId=%22Barukcic%22%26any&currentPosition=30>

^m<https://portal.dnb.de/opac/showNextResultSite?currentResultId=%22Barukcic%22%26any&currentPosition=30>